

Studies on the dissociation constants and solubility of amino acids in water + urea mixtures at 298 K, interaction of urea with amino acids and the role of urea in the denaturation of proteins in terms of structural aspects of water[†]

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Abstract : The first and second dissociation constants of amino acids (glycine, L-proline, L-valine, α -alanine, β -alanine, L-asparagine, L-methionine, L-leucine, L-threonine, L-glutamine, L-serine and L-histidine) were determined pH-metrically in water + urea (0–8 M urea) mixtures at 298 K. Solubilities of amino acids in water + urea mixtures and the interaction constants of amino acids with urea were also determined pH-metrically.

The Gibbs energies of transfer ΔG_t^0 (1) and ΔG_t^0 (2) for the reactions,

and

were coupled with Gibbs energies of transfer for neutral amino acids [ΔG_t^0 (RH[±])] and H⁺-ions [ΔG_t^0 (H⁺)] (determined previously) to get the Gibbs energies of transfer of RH₂⁺ [ΔG_t^0 (RH₂⁺)] and R⁻ [ΔG_t^0 (R⁻)] from water to water+urea mixtures. ΔG_t^0 (H⁺) were also calculated directly and utilized. ΔG_t^0 (RH₂⁺) and ΔG_t^0 (R⁻) are negative and positive respectively. These give the quantitative measure of ion-solvent interactions of the cations and anions of the amino acids. The interaction constants of amino acids with urea were calculated. The results were discussed in terms of structural changes of water in presence of urea in water + urea mixtures, changed basicities of the solvent mixtures and solute-solvent interactions. However interaction of urea with amino acids appears not to be responsible for the denaturation of proteins but the destruction of the tetrahedral structure of H₂O by urea is responsible for the alteration of protein folding and protein structure leading to denaturation.

Direct mechanism involving microscopic properties suggests that no structure breaking of water by urea but a number of indirect evidences suggest urea to be the structure breaker of water.

Keywords : Amino acids, urea + water mixtures, solubility, dissociation constants, free energy of transfer of single ion values, binding constant, Gibbs energy of H⁺.

Introduction

Water has a unique property of self association due to directional characteristics, its cooperativity and coplanarity and H-bonding capability. Under normal conditions,

it can be regarded to have stable tetrahedral structure. Water is responsible for the dissociation of acids and bases and determines the strength of the acids which is indirectly related to acidity and basicity of water. Introduc-

[†]In honour of Professor Jai P. Mittal.

tion of a second solvent or solute necessarily disturbs the water structure and its acid-base character. Urea with CO and 2-NH₂ groups naturally disrupts the structure of water and self association of water. Urea is known for the denaturation of globular proteins and is related to isothermal unfolding of the protein molecule due to weaker hydrophobic interactions^{1,2}. The appreciable decrease in the catalytic activities of strong acids towards the hydrolysis of esters in presence of urea and the interaction of urea with weak acids like acetic acid, *p*-nitrophenol have been reported by different workers³⁻⁶.

In a series of papers, Lahiri and co-workers⁷⁻¹³ determined the solubility and dissociation constants of amino acids and other weak acids in different aquo + organic mixtures to throw light on the effect of solvents on the solubility and dissociation constants of weak acids and amino acids, the building blocks of proteins. The interaction of amino acids and gelatin in presence of urea in the concentration range of 1-8 mol dm⁻³ were studied by Jana and Moulik¹⁴. They also determined pK₁ and pK₂ of amino acids (glycine, proline, valine, serine, glutamine, tryptophan, arginine, histidine and aspartic acid) in urea + water mixtures at 310 K by taking pH at the half-neutralization point of the acid-base titration curves of amino acids in urea + water mixtures. They also measured the interactions of amino acids and gelatin with urea with pH-meter having a reproducibility of ±0.05 pH units i.e. uncertainty in the determination of pK values is high. No correction was made for the changes in basicities of solvent mixtures due to addition of urea. The re-determination of the dissociation constant values appears desirable. The solubilities of amino acids in urea + water mixtures are not known.

In the present investigation, the first and second dissociation constants of amino acids like glycine, L-proline, L-valine, α-alanine, β-alanine, L-asparagine, L-methionine, L-leucine, L-threonine, L-glutamine, L-serine and L-histidine were determined in urea + water mixtures (0-8 M urea) pH-metrically at 298 K. The interaction constants of amino acids with different percentages of urea were determined at 298 K.

Solubilities of the amino acids in different water + urea mixtures were also determined at 298 K.

The determination of the single ion values of cations

and anions of amino acids was carried out using the Gibbs energy of transfer of H⁺ ion from our previous work¹⁵. However, ΔG⁰_t(H⁺) from water to water + urea were also calculated in the way described before¹⁶, taking only a single standard state.

The results are described in this communication.

Experimental

The amino acids utilized in the present study are of highest purity available from Sigma, E. Merck or B.D.H. The amino acids (except for guaranteed qualities) were purified by crystallization from ethanol + water mixtures. The amino acids were estimated titrimetrically in the usual way using acid-free formaldehyde solution. A.R. grade urea (B.D.H.) were re-crystallized twice from hot ethanol and stored in a desiccator. The other reagents like formaldehyde, HClO₄ and NaOH were of guaranteed quality E. Merck (India). Triply distilled water from all glass distilling set (corning) was used for preparation of experimental solutions. Urea + water mixtures were prepared by adding calculated amounts of urea by weight to definite weight of water. The densities of the mixtures (Table 1) were determined using a pyknometer, properly calibrated with triply distilled water.

The dissociation constants for the reactions (1) and (2) as well as the interaction constants for the reaction (3) can not be determined conductometrically or potentiometrically involving the cell of the type

*E*⁰-values of Ag(S)|AgCl(S) electrodes in urea + water mixtures are not available. Spectrophotometric method is also not suitable for aliphatic amino acids. Naturally, the dissociation constants of the ligands were determined pH-metrically. However, the H⁺ ion concentration determined using glass-calomel electrode in the usual way does not represent the H⁺ ion concentration in urea + water mixtures unless the glass electrodes in urea + water mixtures are precisely calibrated in the way suggested by Van Uitert *et al.*¹⁷ and extensively used by us and others¹⁸⁻²⁵.

For the calibration of glass-calomel electrode in urea + water mixtures, the meter readings of the 10⁻⁴ M HClO₄ in aqueous and mixed solvents were measured.

Table 1. Solubilities (mol dm⁻³) of amino acids in urea + water mixtures at 298.15 K

Wt% of urea	Mole fraction of urea	1/ε × 10 ²	Glycine	α-Alanine	L-Valine	L-Asparagine
0.00	0.0000	1.27	3.334 (3.333)	1.869 (1.867)	0.753 (0.755)	0.226 (0.233 at 30 °C)
5.92	0.0185	1.24	3.219	1.795	0.752	0.243
11.52	0.0376	1.19	3.107	1.762	0.750	0.262
17.25	0.0588	1.17	3.027	1.707	0.749	0.276
22.65	0.0808	1.14	2.900	1.638	0.744	0.288
27.95	0.1042	1.11	2.778	1.578	0.739	0.303
33.08	0.1292	1.08	2.659	1.541	0.734	0.319
38.10	0.1559	1.05	2.510	1.467	0.728	0.330
42.47	0.1818	1.03	2.399	1.421	0.720	0.345
			L-Threonine	L-Methionine	L-Leucine	
0.00	0.0000	1.27	0.822	0.374	0.185 (0.185)	
5.92	0.0185	1.24	0.813	0.393	0.194	
11.52	0.0376	1.19	0.805	0.426	0.207	
17.25	0.0588	1.17	0.789	0.453	0.210	
22.65	0.0808	1.14	0.773	0.484	0.212	
27.95	0.1042	1.11	0.743	0.509	0.216	
33.08	0.1292	1.08	0.712	0.535	0.222	
38.10	0.1559	1.05	0.698	0.546	0.225	
42.47	0.1818	1.03	0.684	0.562	0.231	
			L-Glutamine	L-Serine	L-Histidine	
0.00	0.0000	1.27	0.293	0.476 (0.478)	0.273 (0.27)	
5.92	0.0185	1.24	0.303	0.500	0.288	
11.52	0.0376	1.19	0.315	0.524	0.303	
17.25	0.0588	1.17	0.323	0.535	0.312	
22.65	0.0808	1.14	0.329	0.543	0.318	
27.95	0.1042	1.11	0.331	0.548	0.320	
33.08	0.1292	1.08	0.335	0.556	0.322	
38.10	0.1559	1.05	0.332	0.553	0.320	
42.47	0.1818	1.03	0.330	0.550	0.321	

The correction factors $\log U_H$ in mixed solvents were obtained using the relation

$$\log [H^+] = B + \log U_H$$

where $[H^+]$ represents the stoichiometric H^+ ion concentration $[10^{-4} M HClO_4]$ in aqueous solution and B represents the meter readings of $10^{-4} M HClO_4$ in mixed solvents.

The reliability and reproducibility of the method was checked by comparing the theoretical values of the H^+ concentration of five different solutions of known con-

centrations ($1.5-4 \times 10^{-3} M$) with those obtained using meter readings (B -values) and $\log U_H$ values. The results agree well (within 0.01 pH unit).

For the determination of the acid dissociation constants of amino acids, the meter readings (B -values) of a number of solutions of $HClO_4$ of varying concentration ($3-7 \times 10^{-3} M$) were measured in presence and absence of a definite concentration ($1 \times 10^{-2} M$) of amino acids. The process was the same for each of the amino acids. The differences of H^+ ion concentrations obtained from

the meter readings of the corresponding solutions (with and without amino acids) gave the amount of cations of amino acids (RH_2^+) and the meter readings with proper corrections gave the H^+ ion concentration of the solution. For the determination of the second dissociation constants of the amino acids (alkaline) the procedure was the same, only HClO_4 was replaced by NaOH . For the determination of the second dissociation of histidine the procedure was the same, but the neutralization was made with $(1.3\text{--}1.7 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}) \text{HClO}_4$.

For the determination of solubility of amino acids, saturated solutions of amino acids were made by adding excess acids in urea + water mixtures at about 300 K. The solution was placed in a Campbell solubility apparatus and placed in a thermostat at 298 K for more than six hours and the apparatus was inverted in the thermostat. The amount of amino acids in a known volume of solution was determined gravimetrically by evaporating the solution above 503 K in a porcelain crucible. Water and urea evaporated leaving the amino acid in question. The density of urea + water mixtures in presence and absence of saturated solutions of amino acid were also determined.

The pH-metric measurements were made using Orion Digital pH-meter (Model E_A^{TM} 940 Expandable Ion Analyzer) having a resolution of 0.001 pH unit but the values were rounded up to 0.01 pH unit.

The interaction or binding constants of urea with amino acids were determined from H^+ ion concentrations of amino acids in presence and absence of urea measured against the corresponding blank mixtures.

Results

The dissociation equilibria of amino acids in acid and alkali and the interactions of amino acids with urea are represented by the equations

The dissociation constants K_1 and K_2 for the reactions (1) and (2) are represented by

$$K_1 = \frac{a_{\text{H}^+} \cdot a_{\text{RH}^\pm}}{a_{\text{RH}_2^+}} = \frac{C_{\text{H}^+} \cdot C_{\text{RH}^\pm}}{C_{\text{RH}_2^+}} \times \frac{f_{\text{H}^+} \cdot f_{\text{RH}^\pm}}{f_{\text{RH}_2^+}} \quad (4)$$

$$K_2 = \frac{a_{\text{H}^+} \cdot a_{\text{R}^-}}{a_{\text{RH}^\pm}} = \frac{C_{\text{H}^+} \cdot C_{\text{R}^-}}{C_{\text{RH}^\pm}} \times \frac{f_{\text{H}^+} \cdot f_{\text{R}^-}}{f_{\text{RH}^\pm}} \quad (5)$$

The interaction or binding constants for the reaction (3) is given by

$$K_U = \frac{a_{\text{UH}^+} \cdot a_{\text{R}^-}}{a_{\text{U}} \cdot a_{\text{RH}^\pm}} = \frac{C_{\text{UH}^+} \cdot C_{\text{R}^-}}{C_{\text{U}} \cdot C_{\text{RH}^\pm}} \times \frac{f_{\text{UH}^+} \cdot f_{\text{R}^-}}{f_{\text{U}} \cdot f_{\text{RH}^\pm}} \quad (6)$$

The activity coefficient values of the different forms of amino acids in aqueous and urea + water mixtures are not available. The addition of neutral electrolytes was scrupulously avoided to avoid molecular combinations, if any²⁶. Moreover, the activity coefficients in mixed solvents are likely to change due to (i) salt effect (γ_f) and (ii) the medium effect (γ_m)²⁵.

Addition of neutral electrolytes invariably causes solute-solvent, ion-ion interactions of unknown magnitude which are likely to mask the 'medium effects' for the reactions. Thus, we preferred to work in dilute solutions so that the activity coefficients for all the ionic species in aqueous and mixed solvents can be regarded to be unity and the medium effects may be properly ascertained.

In case of $\text{p}K_1$ values, the effect would be marginal as f_{H^+} and $f_{\text{RH}_2^+}$ cancel each other in the concentration ranges studied and the error due to uncertain f_{RH^\pm} terms may be neglected. But error in case of $\text{p}K_2$ may be higher due to

contributions from $\frac{f_{\text{H}^+} \cdot f_{\text{R}^-}}{f_{\text{RH}^\pm}}$ terms. Moreover, in view

of lack of values of autoprotolysis constants of water in urea + water mixtures, slight error may occur in the evaluation of C_{OH^-} values in urea + water mixtures. But the effect will be small as the determination of C_{OH^-} values of amino acids in urea + water mixtures were made against the suitable blank i.e. urea + water mixtures. Moreover, there are slight fluctuations of e.m.f. readings in the alkaline solution as observed by Edsall and Blanchard even in aqueous solution.

The eqs. (4) and (5) can be rearranged as

$$\text{p}K_1 = B + \log U_{\text{H}} - \log \left(\frac{C}{a - C_{\text{H}^+}} - 1 \right) - \log \frac{f_{\text{H}^+} \cdot f_{\text{RH}^\pm}}{f_{\text{RH}_2^+}} \quad (7)$$

and,

$$pK_2 = B' + \log U_H - \log \left(\frac{C}{b - C_{OH^-}} - 1 \right) - \log \frac{f_{H^+} \cdot f_{R^-}}{f_{RH^+}} \quad (8)$$

Here, C = concentration of neutral amino acid, a or b = concentration of acid or base respectively. C_{H^+}/C_{OH^-} are the concentration of H^+/OH^- ion in the experimental solution determined experimentally. B and B' are the meter readings in acidic or alkaline solutions of amino acids in urea + water mixtures.

The concentrations of amino acids and $HClO_4$ or $NaOH$ used were $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ and $3.0-7.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ respectively.

For the determination of the binding constants of urea with amino acids, eq. (6) was utilized.

$$C_{UH^+} = \text{Concentration of } H^+ \text{ ion from the dissociation of amino acids in water} - \text{Concentration of } H^+ \text{ ion from the dissociation of amino acids in urea + water mixtures} \quad (9)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} C_{RH^+} &= C - C_{UH^+} \\ C_{R^-} &= C_{UH^+} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (10)$$

Discussion

The pK_1 and pK_2 values of different amino acids and the solubilities of the amino acids (except β -alanine and L-proline) at 298 K are reported in Tables 1 and 2. The pK_1 and pK_2 values of amino acids in water agree well with the literature values as reported before.

Jana and Moulik¹⁴ determined pK -values at 310 K of amino acids in water + urea mixtures using pH-titration with an Elico pH-meter with a reproducibility of 0.05 pH units and without any correction for the change in the basicities of solvent mixtures. An error to the extent 0.1 pK in pK -values can be expected. The pK -values determined by us at 298 K and the pK -values reported by Jana and Moulik at 310 K suggest that the temperature coefficients for the dissociation of amino acids are very small.

The pK_1 and pK_2 gradually increase with increase in urea concentration similar to those observed in the cases of other mixed solvents like water + alcohol mixtures, water + dioxane mixtures while decrease in dielectric constant should favor association. However, in water + urea mixtures, the increase in basicity and dielectric constant should favor dissociation or decrease in pK -values but the increase in pK -values must be due to the decrease

in concentration of amino acids in presence of urea due to interaction of urea with Zwitterionic amino acids. Interaction of amino acids with urea has been previously reported and corroborated from the present investigation. However, solute-solvent interactions like hydrophobic interactions may be the reasons for the change.

It may be considered that Zwitterionic character of amino acids will change with increase in the basicity of mixed solvents. But the previous experiments show the conversion of Zwitter ion to neutral forms is small as estimated from the calculation of K_Z values.

$$K_Z = \frac{[NH_3^+ RCO_2^-]}{[NH_2 RCO_2 H]} \quad (11)$$

in the previous experiments^{12,27}.

It was also observed that Gibbs energies of transfer of amino acids [$\Delta G_t^0 (RH^\pm)$] are found to be increasingly favorable in going from water to water + urea mixtures with increased basicities in case of glycine, α -alanine, L-valine, L-threonine but unfavorable in case of L-asparagine, L-methionine, L-leucine, L-glutamine, L-serine and L-histidine.

This anomaly may be due to changed hydrophobic character of the amino acids, their interactions with urea and structural changes of water + urea mixtures.

Gibbs energy changes for the reactions (1) and (2) from water to water+urea mixtures may be useful for understanding the effects of solvents on the dissociation of amino acids which is obviously related to Gibbs energy changes of amino acid ions, amino acids and H^+ ions. However, Gibbs energies of transfer of ions are assumed to give a quantitative measure of ion-solvent interactions.

This can be obtained from the relations

$$\Delta G_t^0 (1) = \Delta G_t^0 (H^+) + \Delta G_t^0 (RH^\pm) - \Delta G_t^0 (RH_2^+) \quad (12)$$

or,

$$\Delta G_t^0 (RH_2^+) = -\Delta G_t^0 (1) + \Delta G_t^0 (H^+) + \Delta G_t^0 (RH^\pm) \quad (13)$$

and,

$$\Delta G_t^0 (R^-) = -\Delta G_t^0 (2) - \Delta G_t^0 (H^+) + \Delta G_t^0 (RH^\pm) \quad (14)$$

$\Delta G_t^0 (H^+)$ values are obtained from our previous works and $\Delta G_t^0 (RH^\pm)$ is obtained from the present work from which $\Delta G_t^0 (RH_2^+)$ and $\Delta G_t^0 (R^-)$ are calculated using the above relations. The values are presented in Tables 3 and 4.

Table 2. Dissociation constants of amino acids in urea + water mixtures at 298.15 K

Wt% of urea	1/ε × 10 ²	Glycine		α-Alanine		β-Alanine		L-Proline		
		pK ₁	pK ₂	pK ₁	pK ₂	pK ₁	pK ₂	pK ₁	pK ₂	
0.00	1.27	2.33 (2.34)	9.59 (9.60)	2.33 (2.34)	9.65 (9.69)	3.57 (3.55)	10.20 (10.24)	1.99 (1.99)	10.60 (10.60)	
5.92	1.24	2.52	9.61	2.53	9.67	3.67	10.21	2.21	10.62	
11.52	1.19	2.62	9.63	2.69	9.69	3.72	10.23	2.39	10.66	
17.25	1.17	2.76	9.65	2.83	9.71	3.83	10.26	2.53	10.67	
22.65	1.14	2.89	9.67	3.01	9.78	3.97	10.29	2.68	10.69	
27.95	1.11	3.04	9.77	3.10	9.83	4.07	1.35	2.78	10.71	
33.08	1.08	3.09	9.85	3.27	9.85	4.28	10.41	2.85	10.79	
38.10	1.05	3.16	9.90	3.32	9.89	4.44	10.47	3.01	10.83	
42.47	1.03	3.29	9.99	3.39	9.95	4.58	10.52	3.12	10.84	
		L-Valine		L-Asparagine		L-Threonine		L-Methionine		
		pK ₁	pK ₂	pK ₁	pK ₂	pK ₁	pK ₂	pK ₁	pK ₂	
0.00	1.27	2.32 (2.32)	9.60 (9.62)	2.28 (2.02)	8.69 (8.80)	2.16 (2.15)	9.02 (9.12)	2.29 (2.28)	9.20 (9.21)	
5.92	1.24	2.48	9.63	2.39	8.72	2.40	9.04	2.39	9.22	
11.52	1.19	2.60	9.67	2.61	8.74	2.52	9.06	2.49	9.23	
17.25	1.17	2.76	9.70	2.91	8.77	2.69	9.10	2.63	9.25	
22.65	1.14	2.83	9.73	3.06	8.79	2.81	9.15	2.79	9.27	
27.95	1.11	2.94	9.80	3.13	8.86	2.94	9.24	2.97	9.33	
33.08	1.08	3.04	9.81	3.17	8.88	3.04	9.25	3.09	9.36	
38.10	1.05	3.18	9.85	3.27	8.93	3.15	9.31	3.32	9.40	
42.47	1.03	3.35	9.91	3.36	8.98	3.22	9.38	3.45	9.45	
		L-Leucine		L-Glutadine		L-Serine		L-Histidine		
		pK ₁	pK ₂	pK ₁	pK ₂	pK ₁	pK ₂	pK ₁	pK ₂	pK ₃
0.00	1.27	2.41 (2.36)	9.59 (9.60)	2.16 (2.17)	9.08 (9.13)	2.22 (2.21)	9.01 (9.15)	1.76 (1.78)	5.96 (5.97)	9.10 (9.10)
5.92	1.24	2.48	9.60	2.39	9.10	2.48	9.04	2.13	5.85	9.12
11.52	1.19	2.53	9.62	2.55	9.12	2.62	9.07	2.32	5.76	9.17
17.25	1.17	2.64	9.66	2.69	9.14	2.78	9.11	2.49	5.73	9.23
22.65	1.14	2.78	9.68	2.78	9.20	2.90	9.16	2.62	5.68	9.26
27.95	1.11	2.89	9.75	2.91	9.30	3.02	9.23	2.77	5.63	9.33
33.08	1.08	3.10	9.78	3.01	9.35	3.13	9.26	2.95	5.58	9.40
38.10	1.05	3.23	9.83	3.15	9.40	3.25	9.32	3.06	5.43	9.45
42.47	1.03	3.36	9.89	3.25	9.48	3.35	9.39	3.18	5.38	9.51

Table 3. Free energies of transfer (ΔG^0_1 (RH[±])) of amino acids in urea + water mixtures at 298.15 K

Wt% of urea	Glycine	α-Alanine	L-Valine	L-Asparagine	L-Threonine
5.92	0.08	0.10	0.003	-0.18	0.027
11.52	0.17	0.15	0.009	-0.37	0.052
17.25	0.24	0.22	0.013	-0.50	0.101
22.65	0.35	0.33	0.029	-0.60	0.152
27.95	0.45	0.42	0.046	-0.73	0.250

Table-3 (contd.)

33.08	0.56	0.48	0.063	-0.85	0.356
38.10	0.70	0.60	0.084	-0.94	0.405
42.47	0.82	0.68	0.111	-1.05	0.455
	L-Methionine	L-Leucine	L-Glutamine	L-Serine	L-Histidine
5.92	-0.12	-0.12	-0.080	-0.12	-0.13
11.52	-0.32	-0.28	-0.180	-0.24	-0.26
17.25	-0.48	-0.31	-0.240	-0.29	-0.33
22.65	-0.64	-0.34	-0.290	-0.33	-0.38
27.95	-0.76	-0.38	-0.300	-0.35	-0.39
33.08	-0.89	-0.45	-0.330	-0.39	-0.41
38.10	-0.94	-0.49	-0.310	-0.37	-0.39
42.47	-1.01	-0.55	-0.295	-0.38	-0.40
ΔG° (s) in water : (in kJ mol ⁻¹)					
	Glycine				
	2.98				
	α -Alanine				
	1.55				
	L-Valine				
	-0.70				
	L-Asparagine				
	-3.68				
	L-Threonine				
	-0.48				
	L-Methionine				
	-2.44				
	L-Leucine				
	-4.18				
	L-Glutamine				
	-3.04				
	L-Serine				
	-1.84				
	L-Histidine				
	-3.22				

Table 4A. Free energy of transfer for the amino acid cations in urea + water mixtures at 298.15 K

Wt% of urea	Glycine (kJ mol ⁻¹)	α -Alanine (kJ mol ⁻¹)	L-Valine (kJ mol ⁻¹)	L-Asparagine (kJ mol ⁻¹)	L-Threonine (kJ mol ⁻¹)
5.92	-3.05	-3.09	-2.95	-2.86	-3.39
11.52	-5.76	-6.18	-5.86	-6.52	-6.28
17.25	-8.94	-9.36	-9.23	-10.88	-9.66
22.65	-11.00	-11.70	-11.03	-13.20	-11.71
27.95	-13.85	-14.23	-13.74	-15.83	-14.45
33.08	-16.05	-17.16	-16.32	-18.20	-16.93
38.10	-17.27	-18.68	-18.46	-20.22	-18.86
42.47	-19.09	-19.80	20.20	-21.65	-20.03
	L-Methionine (kJ mol ⁻¹)	L-Leucine (kJ mol ⁻¹)	L-Glutamine (kJ mol ⁻¹)	L-Serine (kJ mol ⁻¹)	L-Histidine (kJ mol ⁻¹)
5.92	-2.74	-2.57	-3.44	-3.65	-4.29
11.52	-5.73	-5.24	-6.68	-6.79	-7.73
17.25	-9.17	-8.35	-10.00	-10.19	-11.23
22.65	-11.64	-10.60	-11.98	-12.36	-13.44
27.95	-14.89	-13.37	-14.83	-15.17	-16.41
33.08	-17.77	-16.66	-17.45	-17.85	-19.48
38.10	-20.45	-18.80	-19.59	-19.88	-27.45
42.47	-22.06	-20.40	-20.95	-21.26	-28.65

ΔG° (RH₂⁺) in water : (in kJ mol⁻¹)

Glycine	-1103.7
α -Alanine	-1102.4
L-Valine	-1099.6
L-Asparagine	-1096.7
L-Threonine	-1089.8
L-Methionine	-1091.9
L-Leucine	-1096.8
L-Glutamine	-1089.8
L-Serine	-1098.2
L-Histidine	-1118.2

Table 4B. Free energy of transfer for the amino acid anions in urea + water mixtures at 298.15 K

Wt% of urea	Glycine (kJ mol ⁻¹)	α -Alanine (kJ mol ⁻¹)	L-Valine (kJ mol ⁻¹)	L-Asparagine (kJ mol ⁻¹)	L-Threonine (kJ mol ⁻¹)
5.92	2.24	2.26	2.23	2.04	2.19
11.52	4.67	4.65	4.68	4.19	4.55
17.25	7.31	7.29	7.31	7.69	7.29
22.65	8.96	9.22	8.92	8.12	9.04
27.95	11.73	11.70	11.44	10.35	11.76
33.08	14.31	13.89	13.53	12.50	13.94
38.10	16.10	15.60	15.18	14.06	15.70
42.47	17.53	16.82	16.31	15.04	16.95
	L-Methionine (kJ mol ⁻¹)	L-Leucine (kJ mol ⁻¹)	L-Glutamine (kJ mol ⁻¹)	L-Serine (kJ mol ⁻¹)	L-Histidine (kJ mol ⁻¹)
5.92	2.04	1.99	2.08	2.10	2.03
11.52	4.12	4.10	4.32	4.37	4.41
17.25	6.54	6.82	6.83	7.31	7.41
22.65	7.91	8.32	8.55	8.68	8.68
27.95	10.23	10.78	11.21	11.16	11.17
33.08	12.29	12.90	13.48	13.31	13.57
38.10	13.83	14.51	15.15	15.03	15.24
42.47	14.85	15.59	16.42	16.22	16.37

 ΔG° (R⁻) in water : (in kJ mol⁻¹)

Glycine	1139.1
α -Alanine	1140.9
L-Valine	1143.5
L-Asparagine	1140.7
L-Threonine	1092.4
L-Methionine	1090.5
L-Leucine	1146.3
L-Glutamine	1089.8
L-Serine	1138.9
L-Histidine	1140.7

It is difficult to predict the error ranges of $\Delta G_t^0(\text{RH}_2^+)$ and $\Delta G_t^0(\text{R}^-)$ as errors are compounded mainly from $\Delta G_t^0(\text{H}^+)$ and small errors from the experimental values of $\Delta G_t^0(1)$, $\Delta G_t^0(2)$ and $\Delta G_t^0(\text{RH}^\pm)$.

$\Delta G_t^0(\text{H}^+)$ values were determined by us using the 'isoelectronic' reaction.

where L = 1,10-phenanthroline. We also have

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G_t^0(15) &= \Delta G_t^0(\text{L}) + \Delta G_t^0(\text{H}^+) \\ &\quad - \Delta G_t^0(\text{LH}^+) \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

since

$$\Delta G_t^0(\text{LH}^+) = \Delta G_t^0(\text{L}) + \Delta G_{t(\text{el})}^0(\text{LH}^+) \quad (17)$$

$$\Delta G_t^0(\text{H}^+) = \Delta G_t^0(15) + \Delta G_{t(\text{el})}^0(\text{LH}^+) \quad (18)$$

Thus, the method is based on extrathermodynamic assumptions and the error range can be expected to be high ($\pm 0.5 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ to 1.0 kJ mol^{-1}).

However, $\Delta G_t^0(\text{H}^+)$ can be directly calculated in way described previously¹⁶ following the scheme

Gibbs energy of hydration or solvation, $\Delta G_{\text{h or s}}^0(\text{H}^+)$ is the summation of three terms i.e. ΔG_{I}^0 , the Gibbs energy change due to deionization (equal to $-I.P.$, the negative ionization potential); ΔG_{II}^0 , the Gibbs energy change to bring gaseous H-atom into the solution and ΔG_{III}^0 , the Gibbs energy of charging solvated H-atom ($=I.P./\epsilon$), where ϵ is the relative permittivity of the solvent in question.

The details were described in a recent paper¹⁶. Obviously, $\Delta G_t^0(\text{H}^+)$ values from water to water + urea mixtures using the two different methods differ considerably (Table 6). $\Delta G_t^0(\text{H}^+)$ values based on the reaction (13) is totally extrathermodynamic in nature. The reaction studied is in different solvent system with different standard states though $\Delta G_t^0(\text{H}^+)$ is based on the standard state water. However, in the direct calculation of $\Delta G_t^0(\text{H}^+)$ a single standard state i.e. Gibbs energy and enthalpy change of $\text{H}_2(\text{g})$ at 1 atm. press. and 298 K is taken to be zero for all the solvents and solvent mixtures. Thus a reasonable difference between the two sets of values exists.

In our experiments, standard states differ from solvent to solvent but efforts have been made to correlate

the results with respect to water as standard state where e.m.f. of H_2 electrode is known to be zero.

The single ion values of the respective cations $\Delta G_t^0(\text{RH}_2^+)$ and anions $\Delta G_t^0(\text{R}^-)$ of amino acids are given in Table 4.

The interaction constant of amino acids with urea would be same irrespective of the amino acids if H^+ ion comes from the dissociation of amino acids as shown by the equation

as observed in case of interaction of urea with different acids like HNO_3 , H_2SO_4 , HClO_4 , acetic acid but if the interaction is due to the reaction (3) where amino acids directly interact with urea, the values would be different as given in Table 5. It is expected that amino acids with similar acid dissociation constants would have almost the same interaction constants.

Though many of the amino acids are less soluble in water but in all cases $\Delta G_t^0(\text{RH}_2^+)$ from water to water + urea mixture and $\Delta G_t^0(\text{R}^-)$ from water to water + urea mixture are favorable.

The interaction of urea with amino acids has been suggested to be a possible reason for the denaturation of proteins by urea¹⁴. But the amino acid-urea interaction has nothing to do with protein denaturation. Proteins usually become positively charged and negatively charged depending on the pH of the media. The behavior of water molecules at the interface of protein is important. Water is anisotropic in nature. Due to cooperativity, H-bonding ability (ability of self-assembly) and directional properties of water, water interacts with hydrophobic moieties of the bio-molecules like protein and orients them. All the anomalous properties of the most abundant miraculous solvent water and the important biological compounds like proteins, nucleic acids etc. are not understood properly. But water plays a crucial role in protein folding i.e. the process by which each protein acquires a functionally effective unique three dimensional shape. In spite of numerous folding configurations possible, a protein always reverts to its own unique configuration. It is believed that hydrophobic interactions between water and protein molecules and the hydrogen-bonding are the main driving forces in protein folding. As a result proteins (other molecules also) fold, assume shape, assemble etc. DNA forms

Table 5. Binding constants (K_D) of amino acids in urea + water mixtures at 298.15 K

Concentration of urea (M)	wt% of urea	Glycine	L-Proline	α -Alanine	β -Alanine
1	5.92	1.82	1.63	1.69	1.95
2	11.52	1.84	1.68	1.73	2.00
3	17.25	2.03	1.97	2.03	2.08
4	22.65	2.56	2.08	2.83	2.90
5	27.95	2.90	2.15	3.04	3.61
6	33.08	3.16	2.66	3.16	4.42
7	38.10	3.45	2.98	4.07	5.04
8	42.47	3.83	3.48	5.09	5.59
		L-Valine	L-Asparagine	L-Threonine	L-Methionine
1	5.92	1.69	1.75	1.40	1.81
2	11.52	1.73	1.79	1.49	1.84
3	17.25	2.03	1.87	1.54	2.02
4	22.65	2.76	2.08	1.78	2.19
5	27.95	3.04	2.20	2.04	2.50
6	33.08	3.16	2.47	2.36	2.80
7	38.10	3.98	2.84	2.71	3.21
8	42.47	5.21	3.24	3.24	3.92
		L-Leucine	L-Glutamine	L-Serine	L-Histidine
1	5.92	1.69	1.34	2.02	1.63
2	11.52	1.73	1.68	2.51	1.73
3	17.25	1.82	1.72	2.64	1.77
4	22.65	2.03	1.88	2.83	2.03
5	27.95	2.15	2.09	3.04	2.20
6	33.08	2.60	2.36	3.24	2.47
7	38.10	2.91	2.64	3.79	2.91
8	42.47	3.32	3.24	4.63	3.16

Table 6

Wt% of urea	$1/\epsilon \times 10^2$	ρ_s (gms/cc)	M_s	V_s	$\sigma_s (n^0)$	σ_1 (SPT)	σ_{12}
0.00	1.27	0.99712	18.03	18.08	3.86	2.73	2.730
5.92	1.24	1.01108	18.81	18.60	3.89	2.76	2.745
11.52	1.19	1.02753	19.61	19.09	3.93	2.80	2.765
17.25	1.17	1.05336	20.51	19.47	3.95	2.84	2.785
22.65	1.14	1.07016	21.43	20.03	3.99	2.86	2.795
27.95	1.11	1.10321	22.42	20.32	4.01	2.88	2.805
33.08	1.08	1.14091	23.46	20.56	4.02	2.88	2.805
38.10	1.05	1.16323	24.59	21.14	4.06	2.92	2.825
42.47	1.03	1.20083	25.66	21.37	4.08	2.94	2.835
		Y	K_0 (cals mol ⁻¹)	K_1 (cals mol ⁻¹ Å ⁻¹)	K_2 (cals mol ⁻¹ Å ⁻²)	K_3 (cals mol ⁻¹ Å ⁻³)	
0.00	1.27	0.3547	1065.023	-1895.461	956.480		
5.92	1.24	0.3563	1078.644	-1895.404	945.118		
11.52	1.19	0.3625	1131.641	-1952.101	955.022		

Table-6 (contd.)

17.25	1.17	0.3706	1227.920	-2039.739	977.666	
22.65	1.14	0.3681	1178.153	-1988.179	948.386	0.06107
27.95	1.11	0.3705	1198.296	-2007.693	949.402	
33.08	1.08	0.3662	1158.603	-1949.684	924.546	
38.10	1.05	0.3710	1204.800	-1988.694	926.885	
42.47	1.03	0.3748	1297.972	-2025.938	935.287	
		ΔG_c^0	$RT \ln (RT/V_s)$	ΔG_{II}^0	$\Delta G_{h \text{ or } s}^0 (H^+)$	$\delta \Delta G_{t(w \rightarrow s)}^0 (H^+)$
				(kJ mol ⁻¹)		
0.00	1.27	12.64	12.20	24.84	-1269.4	0.0
5.92	1.24	12.55	12.13	24.68	-1269.9	0.5
11.52	1.19	12.70	12.06	24.76	-1270.5	1.1
17.25	1.17	13.10	12.00	25.10	-1270.5	1.1
22.65	1.14	12.68	11.94	24.62	-1271.3	1.9
27.95	1.11	12.71	11.91	24.62	-1271.7	2.3
33.08	1.08	12.41	11.88	24.29	-1272.4	3.0
38.10	1.05	12.49	11.81	24.30	-1273.3	3.9
42.47	1.03	12.61	11.78	24.39	-1273.0	3.6

helices able to zip and unzip, enzymes possess their 3D structures and biocatalytic activities due to hydrogen bonding abilities and collective behavior of water molecules. Aggregation of bio-molecular structures, bio-catalytic activities of enzymes and lipid membrane delimited cellular entity are not possible in non-aqueous solvents²⁸⁻³².

Urea (a known chaotrope) with multiple centers of lone pair electrons is a structure breaker of water i.e. it can form H-bonds with water molecules, increases water-water interactions^{33,34} leading to the destruction of self-assembly and most energetically favorable tetrahedral structure of water i.e. urea weakens both hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic interactions³⁵ causing denaturation of proteins. Urea, if present, in small amounts, may not destruct the protein molecules in solutions. But with increase in concentration of urea, urea destroys not only the tetrahedral water structure and self assembly of water but also destroys H-bonds of proteins. The loss of water molecule and structural changes are responsible for protein denaturation during frying of eggs or boiling of eggs.

The illness due to dehydration in man is probably associated with structural breakdown or conversion of protein structure in the body system associated with other effects due to loss of water.

The effect of urea on the properties of aqueous solution, aqueous micellar solutions and protein denaturation

were studied extensively³⁶⁻⁴⁵. The probe to study the effect of urea on the system cited before gave conflicting ideas or mechanisms⁴⁶⁻⁴⁸.

Briganti *et al.*³⁶ have classified the mechanism for action of urea in two categories :

- **Direct mechanism** : i.e. the probe at the molecular level involving studies using computer simulations^{49,50} and electron-spin resonance spectroscopy⁵¹ suggests urea to have negligible effect on water structure, only replacement of some water molecules in the hydration shell around the solute has been observed.

However, in the microscopic experiments, the most favorable and stable energetic state of water, i.e. tetrahedral structure is lost. Water is converted to least favorable energetic monomeric/dimeric state which rules out the possibility of structural breakdown of water by urea.

- **Indirect mechanism** : The mechanism suggests urea to act as structure breaker of water and is responsible for the denaturation of proteins and decreased stability of detergent molecules in water. The reasons advanced are : (i) enhancement of hydrophobic character of the solvent mixtures or (ii) change in the hydrophobic/hydrophilic interactions of the surfactants. Other indirect evidences for considering urea to be a structure breaker can be had from the studies of viscosity *B*-coefficient values⁴⁰, ultrasonic absorption measurements^{41,42} and increase in di-

electric constants of water in presence of urea³⁸ and similar other experimental and physical evidences.

Studies on the role of H₂O²⁸⁻³⁰ conclusively show that self-assembly and directional properties of water due to H-bonding are responsible for the stability of aqueous micellar solutions and proteins which are lost due to structure breaking of water by urea. Thus, in spite of conflicting evidences, the indirect mechanism is widely accepted. However, the conflicting views regarding the role of urea in protein denaturation arise due to flexibility and anomalous properties of water structure. The knowledge of structural behavior of water is only partially unveiled in spite of extensive studies, using theoretical equations, structural model and computer simulations^{32,52}. Molecular models were developed to explain the properties and structure of water and a recent review listed 46 distinct models but their success in quantitatively reproducing the properties of real water is poor though they offer useful insight into water's behavior. But it is certain that water is capable of forming self associated tetrahedral molecule through hydrogen bonding of low potential energy having transient existence (10⁻¹² s). (The life time of any clustered configuration is usually brief). There is a progressive making and breaking of H-bonds in the system. This leads to the high mobility of water molecules, the high mobility of H⁺ and OH⁻ ions in water. These properties are absent in other hydrogen bonded solvents like alcohols. Thus the mobility of water will be reduced in micellar solutions, in aquo + organic solvents, in studies of structure of water with ultrafast probes.

Hydrogen bonding is energetically more favorable than dipolar interactions and make water molecules to order themselves and inhibits random motion. The lowest energy state for water corresponds to four hydrogen bonds with energy increasing successively through three, two, one to a free water molecule. The orientation dependent properties and tetrahedral structure is modified or lost in presence of alcohols, urea particularly in excess. The change in the tetrahedral structure may have secondary effect on the folded structures of proteins, enzymes.

There is structural flexibility of water as reflected in the structural relaxation following an external perturbation or fluctuations within network of hydrogen bonding^{53,54}. It is apparent that the bulk properties are different from microscopic or intrinsic properties related to a

few molecules under conditions of strain (under confined environment or under extreme pressure and temperature^{53,54}). The concept of water or water clusters depends on both time frame and volume under considerations.

Macroscopic properties are determined by the total number of molecules in the bulk and their structural characteristics in the normal states. Thus, the conclusions derived from the macroscopic and microscopic experiments differ widely and they supplement each other.

It may be mentioned in this connection that the simple theory and experimental methods like ion cyclotron resonance and pulsed double resonance⁵⁵ suggest that the order of basicity for the following molecule as

in the gas phase and at the microscopic level where the basicity is the intrinsic property of the molecule. But the basicity is reversed in the solution or bulk phase where the basicity belongs to the entire phase and has less localized meaning and urea with multiple lone pair of electrons may be regarded to be a structure breaker.

Almost all the reactions in biological world, chemical world are macroscopic in nature and macroscopic properties under normal conditions of temperature and pressure are more relevant than microscopic properties though microscopic experiments can give a better idea of the reactions at the molecular level.

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